

ANALYSIS OF SOLVENCY RATIO AND PROFITABILITY RATIO TO STOCK RETURN

(Study on Health Sector Companies Listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2020 – 2022)

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ABSTRACT

This research is a quantitative descriptive research using secondary data collection through documentation. The sample consisted of 13 health companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2020 - 2022 which were obtained by *purposive sampling*. The data analysis method used is the multiple regression analysis method. Classical assumption tests, simultaneous tests (F), and partial tests (T) were used to analyze the data with EViews software 12.

The results of this study are partial, namely the solvency variable (DAR) has a significant effect on *return* stocks while the profitability variable (ROE) has no effect on *return* stock. Meanwhile, solvency (DAR) and profitability (ROE) simultaneously have a significant effect on *return* stock.

(Keywords: Solvency Ratio (DAR), Profitability Ratio (ROE) Return on Shares)

INTRODUCTION

The capital market plays an important role in a country's economy because it carries out two functions at once: economic functions and financial functions. One of the most common methods for analyzing financial information is to use financial ratios. The results of the financial ratio can be used as a basis to influence fluctuations *return* shares in an issuer. Before buying stocks, investors should use the company's financial ratios as the basis for consideration. If the risk of stock price fluctuations due to external factors may be tolerated, but on the other hand, if there are internal factors, then the transparency of the issuer is questionable. Whether or not the issuer is able to manage these internal factors, investors must get clarity and trust from the issuer they are invited to work with. The profitability ratio in this case is only analysed by using *Return on Equity* (ROE) is a measure of the ability of a

company (issuer) to generate profits using its own capital, so this ROE is often referred to as its own capital profitability and solvency in this case is only analysed using *Debt to Assets Ratio* (DAR) is a ratio used to see how much the company's assets are funded by debt or how much the company's debt affects the company's asset management.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Debt to Assets Ratio (DAR)

This ratio is used to determine the extent or size of the assets of a company that relies on debt. *Debt to Assets Ratio* (DAR) compares the total liabilities that must be fulfilled by a company with the total assets owned by the company. This means how much the company's assets are financed by debt and how much debt affects asset management.

The debt to
formula is

$$\text{Debt to Assets Ratio} = \frac{\text{Total Debt}}{\text{Total Asset}}$$

assets ratio
as follows:

2. Return on Equity (ROE)

Return On Equity or the profitability of own capital is a ratio to measure net profit after tax with own capital. This ratio shows the efficiency of the users of their own capital. The higher this ratio, the better. This means that the position of the company owner is getting stronger, and vice versa.

According to (Tandelilin, 2002) *Return On Equity* (ROE) reflects how much a company has earned on the funds that have been invested by shareholders. ROE is important to assess a company's financial performance in meeting shareholder expectations. Formula for searching *Return on Equity* (ROE) can be used as follows:

$$\text{Return On Equity (ROE)} = \frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Total Equity}}$$

3. Return on Shares

The definition of *stock return* is "the rate of return expected by investors in the form of profits from stock profits. (Tandelilin, 2013)

- **Signalling Theory**

In 1973, an expert named Spence was the first to initiate the *signalling theory* or signal theory which describes that the sender provides a signal in the form of information that presents the condition of a company to investors. The use of signal theory is related to profitability, because profitability is considered to give a signal for investors to make investments. Companies that are able to generate high profitability are considered able to provide profits for investors who invest in the company. The relationship between solvency and signal theory is that if a company has a large solvency value, this matter shows that industries that have a large amount of debt so that the risks borne by the industry are also large, as long as economic conditions are difficult or interest rates are large, industries with large solvency can face financial problems. But as long as economic conditions are normal and interest rates are low, it is likely that the debt owned by the industry will be able to pay it off.

RESEARCH METHODS

Figure 2. 1 Framework of Thought

Information:

X1 : Solvency Ratio (Independent variable)

X2 : Profitability Ratio (Independent variable)

Y : Return Stocks (Variable dependent)

—————> : Partial effect of variable X on variable Y

- - - - - : Simultaneous effect of variable X on variable Y

Based on the explanation of the theoretical framework above, the hypothesis of this study is:

1. H1: Solvency ratio has a negative and significant effect on *stock returns*.
2. H2 : The profitability ratio has a positive and significant effect on *stock returns*.
3. H3: Solvency ratio and profitability ratio have a positive and significant effect on *stock returns*.

1. Time and Place of Research

This research was conducted from November 2023 to March 2024. This research was conducted at the Indonesia Stock Exchange located on Jl. Jend. Sudirman, South Jakarta by taking the necessary data through the www.idx.co.id website.

2. Population and Sample

In this study, the population used is health sector companies listed on the IDX through the www.idx.co.id website which totals 28 issuers in 2023

In this study, the technique used is *purposive sampling* , which is the determination of samples with certain considerations.

No.	Criterion	Sum
1	Health sector companies listed on the IDX up to the year of research	28
2	Companies that did not suffer losses during 2020 to 2022	(4)
3	The company provides the data needed in the research	(11)
Number of samples		13

3. Types and Data Sources

The type and source of data used in this study is secondary data, namely data sourced from the annual reports of health sector companies listed on the IDX in 2020 – 2022.

4. Data Collection Methods

The method used by the author to collect the data needed in the research is documentation, which is to obtain data that is carried out by examining company documents related to its financial statements.

5. Data Analysis Methods

The analysis method used is by using a multiple linear regression analysis model. The data analysis of this study uses statistical calculations with the application of Eviews.

A. Classical Assumption Test

- **Multicollinearity Test**

The purpose of this study was to test whether the regression model formed a high or perfect correlation between independent variables. The tolerable correlation value in the multicollinearity test is 70% or 80% (0.7 or 0.8). If the correlation value < 0.7 or < 0.8 , then there is no multicollinearity problem in the research variable.

- **Uji Autokorelasi**

The autocorrelation test is a correlation that occurs between residuals in one observation and other observations in the regression model. Autocorrelation can be determined through the Durbin-Watson Test (D-W Test), autocorrelation can also be determined through the Breusch-Godfrey Test, where if the prob value < 0.05 , autocorrelation symptoms occur while if the prob value > 0.05 , no autocorrelation symptoms occur.

- **Heteroscedasticity Test**

It is used to find out whether or not there is a deviation from classical assumptions. heteroscedasticity is the existence of variant and residual inequality for all observations in the regression model, The requirement that must be met in

the regression model is the absence of heteroscedasticity symptoms. If the prob value is < 0.05 , then heteroscedasticity symptoms occur in the research model, while if the prob value is > 0.05 , then there are no heteroscedasticity symptoms in the research model.

- **Normality Test**

The normality test is used to test whether or not the normalized residual values in the regression model are normally distributed. The normal distributed decision of residual or not can be seen simply by comparing the probability value of J-B (Jarque-Bera) calculated with an alpha level of 0.05 (5%). If the value of the J-B prob is calculated > 0.05 , it can be concluded that the residual is normally distributed. On the other hand, if the J-B prob value is calculated < 0.05 , then there is not enough evidence to state that the residual is normally distributed.

B. Multiple Linear Regression Test

According to (Arifin, 2017), multiple linear regression is that there are two or more independent (free) variables and there is one dependent variable (bound).

$$Y = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + e$$

Information:

Y = Return Stock

X1 = Solvency

X2 = Profitability

a = Constant

B1, B2 = Regression coefficient for each independent variable

e = Disruptive variable

C. Model due diligence (Goodness of Fit)

- **Partial Test (t-Test)**

A partial test (t-test) is a test that is carried out to see whether an independent variable influences the dependent variable by comparing the t_{count} value with the t_{table} .

The test criteria for t-test are as follows:

- If the t_{count} value $> t_{\text{table}}$, the hypothesis is rejected, meaning that the variable influences the dependent variable.
- If the t_{count} value is $< t_{\text{table}}$, the hypothesis is accepted, meaning that the variable has no effect on the dependent variable.

- **Simultaneous Test (Test F)**

Simultaneous test (F test) is a test that is carried out to see whether all independent variables together have the same effect or not on the dependent variable by comparing the value of F_{count} with F_{table} .

- If the value of $F_{\text{count}} > F_{\text{table}}$, the hypothesis is rejected, meaning that together the independent variables influence the dependent variables.
- If the value of $F_{\text{count}} < F_{\text{table}}$, the hypothesis is accepted, meaning that together the independent variables have no effect on the dependent variables.

- **Determinant Coefficient Test (R2)**

The model feasibility test is an R2 test to see the ability of independent variables to explain dependent variables. The R2 value ranges from 0 – 99, the R Square value is closer to 1, the more feasible a model is to use.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Classical Assumption Test

- **Normality Test**

Series: Standardized Residuals	
Sample	2020 2022
Observations	21
Mean	2.85e-16
Median	-0.069415
Maximum	3.011584
Minimum	-3.949767
Std. Dev.	1.576268
Skewness	-0.429835
Kurtosis	3.323267
Jarque-Bera	0.738092
Probability	0.691394

Table 4.1. Normality Test

Source: EViews 12 data processing

Decision making hypothesis:

- a. If the probability value of Jarque-Bera > 0.05 , it can be said that the data used is distributed normally.
- b. If the probability value of Jarque-Bera < 0.05 , it can be said that the data used is abnormally distributed.

In table 4.1. It can be seen that the value of probability of 0.691394 this means that the value of probability > 0.05 can be said that the data is distributed normally.

• **Multicollinearity Test**

	X1	X2	Y
X1	1.000000	0.032667	0.034410
X2	0.032667	1.000000	0.060901
Y	0.034410	0.060901	1.000000

Table 4.2. Multicollinearity Test

Source: EViews 12 data processing

Table 4.2. is the result of the multicollinearity test. One way to analyze the presence or absence of the influence of multicollinearity in this study is to look at the *Correlation Matrix* value using Eviews 12 software. A data can be said to be free from the symptoms of multicollinearity if the correlation value between independent variables is less than 0.8 ($correlation < 0.8$).

In table 4.2. It can be seen that the data does not have a multicollinearity problem because the correlation between variables is less than 0.8.

• **Heteroscedasticity Test**

Heteroskedasticity Test: White
Null hypothesis: Homoskedasticity

F-statistic	0.125129	Prob. F(5,33)	0.9857
Obs*R-squared	0.725639	Prob. Chi-Square(5)	0.9815
Scaled explained SS	4.091487	Prob. Chi-Square(5)	0.5363

Table 4.3. Heteroscedasticity Test

Source: EViews 12 data processing

Decision making hypothesis:

- a) If the White value > 0.05 , then there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity.
- b) If the White value < 0.05 , then the symptoms of heteroscedasticity occur.

In table 4.3, it can be seen that the value of *probability* $0.9815 > 0.05$ so it can be concluded that there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity in this study.

- **Uji Autokorelasi**

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:
Null hypothesis: No serial correlation at up to 2 lags

Table 4. 1 Uji Autokorelasi

F-statistic	1.024510	Prob. F(2,34)	0.3698
Obs*R-squared	2.216753	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.3301

Source: EViews 12 data processing

Decision making hypothesis:

- If the prob value > 0.05 , then no autocorrelation symptoms occur.
- If the prob value < 0.05 , then autocorrelation symptoms occur.

In table 4.4, it can be seen that the value of *probability* $0.3301 > 0.05$, it can be concluded that there are no autocorrelation symptoms in this study.

2. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1.789812	0.574864	3.113452	0.0051
X1	-5.445591	1.836960	-2.964459	0.0072
X2	0.171716	1.515496	0.113307	0.9108

Table 4. 2 Multiple Regression Test

Results

Source: EViews 12 data processing

Based on table 4.5 above, the regression test results using the application of the following equation model:

$$Y = 1.789812 - 5.445591X1 + 0.171716X2 + e$$

Regarding the regression equation above, it can be explained as follows:

- The value of the constant coefficient is 1.789812, meaning that if the independent variables, namely *Debt to Assets Ratio* and *Return on Equity*, have a constant value (value 0), then the dependent variable, namely *Return on Equity*, will be valued at 1.789812.
- The value of the variable regression coefficient X1 is $- 5.445591$, it can be interpreted that if the value of *the Debt to Assets Ratio* increases by 1%, the value of *stock returns* will decrease by $- 5.445591$. This applies the other way around, if the *Debt to Assets Ratio* decreases, the *stock return* will increase.

3. The value of the variable regression coefficient X2 is 0.171716, it can be interpreted that if *the value of Return on Equity* increases by 1%, the value of *stock return* will increase by 0.171716. A positive relationship between *Return on Equity* and *stock return* indicates a unidirectional relationship, namely if the higher *the Return on Equity*, the higher the *stock return*. Likewise, the lower the *Return on Equity*, the lower *the return on the stock*.

3. Model Feasibility Test (*Goodness of Fit*)

- **Partial Test (t-Test)**

Partial hypothesis testing is used to determine the influence of each independent variable on the bound variable. The partial hypothesis test was carried out based on the value of t calculation and t table on the condition that the significant test that the Prob value < 0.05 had been met.

Using the hypothesis:

Ho: Neither effect

Ha: Influential

- a. If the tcount value $<$ ttable, it means that Ho is accepted and Ha is rejected
- b. If the tcount value $>$ ttable, it means that Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted

The value of the table at $\alpha = 0.05$, the number of observations 39 and the free variable = 2 (the value in lines 39 – 3) then the value of the table is 1.68830.

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1.789812	0.574864	3.113452	0.0051
X1	-5.445591	1.836960	-2.964459	0.0072
X2	0.171716	1.515496	0.113307	0.9108

**Table 4. 3 Partial Test Results
(t-Test)**

Source: EViews 12 data processing

Based on the test results of the table above, the partial test can be explained as follows:

- a. The X1 variable shows a calculated t value of $- 2.964459 >$ t table 1.68830 and a prob value of $0.0072 < 0.05$. Thus, it can be concluded that the result of

X1 (Solvency Ratio measured by *Debt to Assets Ratio*) has a significant effect on stock returns. H1 accepted.

- b. The X2 variable shows a calculated t value of $0.113307 < t \text{ table } 1.68830$ and a prob value of $0.9108 > 0.05$. Thus, it can be concluded that the X2 result (Profitability Ratio measured by *Return on Equity*) has no significant effect on stock returns. H2 was rejected.

- **Simultaneous Test (Test F)**

Simultaneous tests are used to see the influence of independent variables together on bound variables. The F test was carried out by comparing F calculation tables. The guidelines used to accept or reject a hypothesis are:

- a. If $F_{\text{calung}} < F_{\text{table}}$, then H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected.
- b. If $F_{\text{calung}} > F_{\text{table}}$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted.

The value of F of the table can be seen in the table F of statistics $df_1 = \text{number of variables} - 1$ or $3 - 1 = 2$ and $df_2 = n - k$ or $39 - 3 = 36$. With a significance of 0.05, the result of table $F = 3.26$ was obtained

R-squared	0.736941	Mean dependent var	0.153369
Adjusted R-squared	0.705993	S.D. dependent var	0.802391
S.E. of regression	0.435076	Akaike info criterion	1.292616
Sum squared resid	6.435892	Schwarz criterion	1.505893
Log likelihood	-20.20601	Hannan-Quinn criter.	1.369138
F-statistic	23.81216	Durbin-Watson stat	2.026330
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Table 4. 4 Simultaneous Test Results (Test F) *Source: EViews 12 data processing*

Based on the results of the F Test, it shows that the F value is calculated as $23.81216 > F_{\text{table}} 3.26$ and the prob value is $0.00000 < 0.05$. Thus, it can be concluded that independent variables simultaneously have a significant effect on stock returns. H3 accepted.

- **Coefficient of Determination (R2)**

The Coefficient of Determination is used to determine the percentage of influence of the independent variable on the bound variable. The independent variable in question is the solvency ratio and the profitability ratio as well as the bound

variable, namely the return on shares. The value of the determination coefficient is measured by the value *of the Adjusted R-Square*.

Based on table 4.6, it can be seen that the *Adjusted R-Square* value of 0.705993 means that the influence of the solvency ratio and the probability ratio on stock *returns* is 70.5993%, while the remaining 29.4007% is influenced by other variables that are not studied or not included in this research model.

CONCLUSION

1. The solvency ratio proxied by *the Debt to Assets Ratio* has a significant effect on stock *returns* in health sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2020 – 2022. This is shown by a significance value of 0.0072 which is smaller than 0.05, so H1 is accepted, which means that there is an effect of *the Debt to Assets Ratio* on stock *returns*.
2. The profitability ratio proxied by *Return on Equity* has no effect on stock *returns* in health sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2020 – 2022. This is shown by a significance value of 0.9108 which is greater than 0.05, so H2 is rejected which means that there is no effect *of Return on Equity* on stock *returns*.
3. The results of the F test in this study show that *Debt to Assets Ratio* and *Return on Equity* have a simultaneous effect on stock *returns* in health sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2020 – 2022. This is shown by the calculated F value of 23.81216 and the significance value of 0.00000 which is smaller than 0.05, so that H3 is accepted, which means that there is a simultaneous influence of *Debt to Assets Ratio* and *Return on Equity* on stock *returns*.
4. Based on the results of the test of the value of the determination coefficient (*Adjusted R Square*) of 0.705993 or 70.5993%, which shows that the influence of independent variables on stock *returns* is 70.5993% while the remaining 29.4007% is influenced by other variables that are not studied or not included in this research model.

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